

Supplementary Notes

This document is the supplementary material for the manuscript “A Deep Learning-based Quality Assessment and Segmentation System with a Large-scale Benchmark Dataset for Optical Coherence Tomographic Angiography Image”.

Table S1

3 × 3 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of ResNet-101, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	93.94	93.00	93.47	83.62	97.00	89.81	87.79	96.80	92.07
Gradable	72.88	86.00	78.90	75.76	75.00	75.38	88.72	77.35	82.65
Outstanding	87.95	73.00	79.78	92.94	79.00	85.41	80.33	82.28	81.29
Macro average	84.92	84.00	84.05	84.11	83.67	83.53	85.61	85.48	85.34
Weighted average	84.92	84.00	84.05	84.11	83.67	83.53	87.12	87.05	86.83

Table S2

3 × 3 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of Inception-V3, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	1.00	92.00	95.83	94.17	97.00	95.57	96.06	94.03	95.03
Gradable	76.42	94.00	84.30	82.23	82.00	82.41	89.77	87.87	88.81
Outstanding	91.76	78.00	84.32	87.76	86.00	86.87	80.69	91.26	85.65
Macro average	89.40	88.00	88.15	88.25	88.33	88.28	88.84	91.06	89.83
Weighted average	89.40	88.00	88.15	88.25	88.33	88.28	91.42	91.20	91.26

Table S3

3 × 3 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of Efficienet-B7, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	96.77	90.00	93.26	92.23	95.00	93.60	94.69	92.07	93.36
Gradable	73.44	94.00	82.46	75.22	85.00	79.81	85.81	87.19	86.50
Outstanding	94.94	75.00	83.80	91.67	77.00	83.70	81.44	85.19	93.27
Macro average	88.38	86.33	86.51	86.37	85.67	85.70	87.31	88.15	87.71
Weighted average	88.38	86.33	86.51	86.37	85.67	85.70	89.32	89.17	89.23

Table S4

3 × 3 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of SE-ResNeXt-101, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	98.88	88.00	93.12	97.00	97.00	97.00	95.75	93.38	94.55
Gradable	67.59	98.00	80.00	70.80	97.00	91.96	85.78	92.62	89.07
Outstanding	96.97	64.00	77.11	1.00	63.00	77.30	91.48	78.16	84.29
Macro average	87.81	83.33	83.41	89.27	85.67	85.39	91.00	88.05	89.30
Weighted average	87.81	83.33	83.41	89.27	85.67	85.39	91.19	90.96	90.94

Table S5

3 × 3 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of Swin-Transformer-Large, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	97.87	92.00	94.85	96.97	96.00	96.48	97.25	95.12	96.17
Gradable	77.87	95.00	85.59	82.88	92.00	87.20	91.02	92.03	91.52
Outstanding	94.63	81.00	88.04	94.44	85.00	89.47	86.71	90.29	88.47
Macro average	90.72	89.33	89.49	91.43	91.00	91.05	91.66	82.48	92.05
Weighted average	90.72	89.33	89.49	91.43	91.00	91.05	93.31	93.22	93.25

Table S6

6 × 6 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of ResNet-101, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	93.94	93.00	93.47	94.25	82.00	87.70	92.11	89.57	90.82
Gradable	77.78	84.00	80.77	64.34	83.00	72.49	80.00	83.53	81.73
Outstanding	89.25	83.00	86.01	84.52	71.00	77.17	82.17	79.82	80.98
Macro average	86.99	86.67	86.75	81.04	78.67	79.12	84.76	84.30	84.51
Weighted average	86.99	86.67	86.75	81.04	78.67	79.12	85.58	85.42	85.47

Table S7

6 × 6 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of Inception-V3, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	93.94	93.00	93.47	89.58	86.00	87.76	93.11	93.80	93.45
Gradable	83.81	88.00	85.85	64.84	83.00	72.81	85.68	84.77	85.22
Outstanding	93.75	90.00	91.84	88.16	67.00	76.14	84.07	84.51	84.29
Macro average	90.50	90.33	90.39	80.86	78.67	78.90	87.62	87.69	87.65
Weighted average	90.50	90.33	90.39	80.86	78.67	78.90	88.56	88.58	88.57

Table S8

6 × 6 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of Efficienet-B7, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	95.10	97.00	96.04	89.47	85.00	87.18	92.68	92.89	92.79
Gradable	82.14	72.00	86.79	62.59	87.00	72.80	82.41	87.07	84.68
Outstanding	96.51	83.00	89.25	93.94	62.00	74.70	88.26	77.34	82.44
Macro average	91.25	90.67	90.69	82.00	78.00	78.23	87.79	85.77	86.64
Weighted average	91.25	90.67	90.69	82.00	78.00	78.23	87.88	87.76	87.73

Table S9

6 × 6 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of SE-ResNeXt101, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	95.88	93.00	94.42	95.74	90.00	92.78	95.09	93.97	94.52
Gradable	87.63	85.00	86.29	79.25	84.00	81.55	89.15	87.32	88.23
Outstanding	89.62	95.00	92.23	87.00	87.00	87.00	85.40	91.41	88.30
Macro average	91.04	91.00	90.98	87.33	87.00	87.11	89.88	90.90	90.35
Weighted average	91.04	91.00	90.98	87.33	87.00	87.11	90.99	90.92	90.93

Table S10

6 × 6 mm² sOCTA quality assessment model results of Swin-Transformer-Large, for each dataset.

	Internal testing set			External testing set			Testing set		
	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score	Precision	Accuracy	F ₁ score
Ungradable	94.68	89.00	91.75	89.11	90.00	89.55	93.24	91.03	92.12
Gradable	78.18	86.00	81.90	59.09	78.00	67.24	81.32	84.96	83.10
Outstanding	89.58	86.00	87.76	83.58	56.00	67.07	82.79	79.56	81.14
Macro average	87.48	87.00	87.14	77.26	74.67	74.62	85.78	85.18	85.46
Weighted average	87.48	87.00	87.14	77.26	74.67	74.62	86.69	86.55	86.59

Fig. S1 Results visualization of ResNet-101, for $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set (left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S2 Results visualization of Inception-V3, for $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S3 Results visualization of Efficienet-B7, for $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S4 Results visualization of SE-ResNeXt-101, for $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S5 Results visualization of Swin-Transformer-Large, for 3×3 mm² sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S6 Results visualization of ResNet-101, for $6 \times 6 \text{ mm}^2$ sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S7 Results visualization of Inception-V3, for $6 \times 6 \text{ mm}^2$ sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S8 Results visualization of EfficientNet-B7, for $6 \times 6 \text{ mm}^2$ sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S9 Results visualization of SE-ResNeXt-101, for $6 \times 6 \text{ mm}^2$ sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).

Fig. S10 Results visualization of Swin-Transformer-Large, for 6×6 mm² sOCTA quality assessment. (a) – (c) ROC curve of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right); (d) – (f) Confusion Matrix plot of predictions of testing set(left), internal testing set (middle) and external testing set (right).